

The Effect of Information Technology, Innovation and Competence on Employee Satisfaction Impact on Employee Performance of PT. PLN (Persero) ULP Pendopo

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ABSTRACT : The problems in this study are: 1) Is there any influence of Information Technology, Innovation and Competence on Employee Performance? 2) Is there an effect of information technology on employee satisfaction, its impact on employee performance? 3) Is there an effect of innovation on employee satisfaction, its impact on employee performance? 4) Does Competence Influence on Employee Satisfaction Have an Impact on Employee Performance? 5) Is there any influence of information technology on employee performance? 6) Is there any influence of competence on employee performance? 7) Is there an effect of employee satisfaction on employee performance? Variables in this study are information technology, innovation, competence, employee satisfaction impact on employee performance. The population in this study were 120 people with a sample of 55 people. The data used in this study is primary data obtained through the distribution of questionnaires. The data collection method in this research is a questionnaire. The data analysis technique used is path analysis. The results of the analysis show that: 1) Information technology has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction. This shows that the information technology used by employees is in accordance with the work they do so that employees feel satisfied, 2) Innovation has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction. This shows that employees must have innovation in increasing job satisfaction, this can affect employee activities at work, 3) Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction. This shows that employees must have the competence to increase job satisfaction, 4) Information technology has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This shows that the existing information technology in the company can support employee performance, 5) Competence has a positive effect on employee performance. This shows that employees who have competence will improve the performance of these employees, 6) Employee satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. This shows that employee satisfaction can affect performance improvement for employees

KEYWORDS : Influence, Information Technology, Innovation, Competence, Employee Satisfaction, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the important indicators in determining the success of an organization, company or government agency is human resources. Employee performance is the result of a person's work and work behavior in a period, usually 1 year. Then performance can be measured by its ability to complete the tasks and

responsibilities given. This means that performance contains elements of achievement standards that must be met, so that those who achieve the standards that have been set mean good performance or vice versa for those who are not achieved are categorized as underperforming or not good. According to Kasmir (2015: 182). According to Muhammad Busro (2018:102), employee satisfaction is a complex problem because it comes from various elements of work, for example their own type of work, salary/wages, promotions, supervision, co-workers, or work as a whole. Dessler, (2015). Information technology is the actual application to describe the features of human resource practices. Information technology is used to support employee performance including: setting financial and non-financial targets to the company's strategic goals, informing all employees of company goals, taking corrective actions on an ongoing basis. according to Hutagalung&Hermawan, D. (2018: 26) innovation is a new discovery that is different from the previous one in the form of thoughts and ideas that can be developed and implemented so that the benefits are felt.

The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of information technology, innovation and competence on employee performance at PT. PLN ULP Pendopo Penukal Abab Lematang Ilir. To determine the effect of information technology on employee satisfaction, its impact on employee performance at PT. PLN ULP Pendopo Penukal Abab Lematang Ilir. To determine the effect of innovation on employee satisfaction, its impact on employee performance at PT. PLN ULP Pendopo Penukal Abab Lematang Ilir. To find out the influence of competence on employee satisfaction, its impact on employee performance at PT. PLN ULP Pendopo Penukal Abab Lematang Ilir. To determine the effect of information technology on employee performance at PT. PLN ULP Pendopo Penukal Abab Lematang Ilir. To find out the influence of competence on employee performance at PT. PLN ULP Pendopo Penukal Abab Lematang Ilir. To find out Employee Satisfaction Against Employee Performance PT. PLN ULP Pendopo Penukal Abab Lematang Ilir?

Benefits of this research for researchers Researchers can provide an overview of practice and theory that has been obtained during lectures, especially in the concentration of human resources. For companies, this research is expected to be informative study material for companies in improving company goals. And for the Alma mater, the results of the research can be a source of reference for further researchers, especially researchers who have relatively the same topic.

According to Muhammad Busro(2018:89)Performance is the result of work that can be achieved by employees, both individuals and groups within an organization, in accordance with the authority and responsibility given by the organization in an effort to achieve the vision, mission, and goals of the organization concerned by including ability, perseverance, independence, ability to solve problems within limits. the time given is legally, does not violate the law and is in accordance with morals and ethics. The factors that affect employee performance are:Ability Factors and Motivation Factors (Mangkunegara 2013)

According to Muhammad Busro (2018:102), employee satisfaction is a complex problem because it comes from various elements of work, such as their own type of work, salary/wages, promotions, supervision, co-workers, or overall work results.The factors that affect employee satisfaction areOpportunities for advancement, job security, salary, company and management, supervision, intrinsic factors of work, working conditions, social aspects of work, smooth communication among employees, and facilities (Gilmer (in Edy Sutrisno, 2010)

Dessler, (2015). Information technology is the actual application to describe the features of human resource practices. Information technology is used to support employee performance including: setting financial and non-financial targets to the company's strategic goals, informing all employees of company goals, taking corrective actions on an ongoing basis.The components of Information Technology are: Hardware, Software, network and communication, and People (AzharSusanto 2013). Sutirna, H. (2018: 23) states that Innovation is an idea, practical things, methods, methods, man-made goods, which are observed or felt as new for a person or group of people (society).

The factors that influence innovation are:Encouragement from within oneself and encouragement from the environment (In Munandar, 2009). Wibowo (2015) competence is an ability to carry out or perform a job or task based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude required by the job. The factors that

influence competence are beliefs and values, skills, expertise experience, personality characteristics, motivation, emotional issues, intellectual abilities, and organizational culture (Zwell in Wibowo 2016)

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

One of the important indicators in determining the success of an organization, company or government agency is human resources. Employee performance is the result of a person's work and work behavior in a period, usually 1 year. Then performance can be measured by its ability to complete the tasks and responsibilities given. This means that performance contains elements of achievement standards that must be met, so that those who achieve the standards that have been set mean good performance or vice versa for those who are not achieved are categorized as underperforming or not good. According to Kasmir (2015: 182). According to Muhammad Busro (2018:102), employee satisfaction is a complex problem because it comes from various elements of work, for example their own type of work, salary/wages, promotions, supervision, co-workers, or work as a whole. Dessler, (2015). Information technology is the actual application to describe the features of human resource practices. Information technology is used to support employee performance including: setting financial and non-financial targets to the company's strategic goals, informing all employees of company goals, taking corrective actions on an ongoing basis. according to Hutagalung&Hermawan, D. (2018: 26) innovation is a new discovery that is different from the previous one in the form of thoughts and ideas that can be developed and implemented so that the benefits are felt.

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III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

Path Analysis Method

Table 1. estimation With Path Anlysis Method

			Estimate	SE	C.R.	P
X1	<---	Y	,241	,121	1,983	0.047
X2	<---	Y	,164	0.079	2,089	0.037
X3	<---	Y	,197	,097	2,027	.043
X1	<---	Z	,221	,109	2.033	.042
X3	<---	Z	,204	,101	2.031	.042
Y	<---	Z	,423	,476	4,466	0.047

Sumber : SPSS Amos 20, 2021 Data Data Calculation Results

The first hypothesis proposed is to determine whether there is an effect of Information Technology (X1) on job satisfaction (Y). Based on the estimation table of the path analysis method, the CR Value is 1.983>

1.96, while the P value (P-value) is 0.047 which means it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_0 is accepted. This means that there is a positive influence between Information Technology on job satisfaction.

The second hypothesis proposed is to determine whether there is an effect of Innovation (X2) on job satisfaction (Y). Based on the estimation table of the path analysis method, the CR Value is $2.089 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.037, which means it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_0 is accepted. This means that there is a positive influence between innovation on job satisfaction.

The third hypothesis proposed is to determine whether there is an effect of competence (X3) on employee satisfaction (Y). Based on the estimation table of the path analysis method, the CR Value is $2.027 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.043 which means it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_0 is accepted. This means that there is a positive influence between competence on employee satisfaction.

The fourth hypothesis proposed is to determine whether there is an influence of Information Technology (X1) on employee performance (Z). Based on the estimation table of the path analysis method, the CR Value is $2.033 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.042 which means it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_a is accepted. This means that there is a positive influence between Information Technology on employee performance.

The fifth hypothesis proposed is to determine whether there is an effect of Competence (X3) on employee performance (Z). Based on the estimation table for the path analysis method, the CR Value is $2.031 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.042, meaning it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_a is accepted. This means that there is a positive influence between competence on employee performance.

The sixth hypothesis proposed is to determine whether there is an effect of job satisfaction (Y) on employee performance (Z). Based on the estimation table for the path analysis method, the CR Value is $2.031 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.042, meaning it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_a is accepted. This means that there is a positive influence between job satisfaction on employee performance.

Discussion

Effect of Information Technology on Employee Satisfaction

The first hypothesis test states that there is an influence of Information Technology (X1) on job satisfaction (Y). Based on the estimation table of the path analysis method, the CR Value is $1.983 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.047 which means it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_0 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Widhijatmiko Setyo Nugroho, Endah Winarti HS, & M. Taufiq (2019) with results proving that information technology affects employee performance. Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance on employee performance.

Impact of Innovation on Employee Satisfaction

The second hypothesis test states that there is an effect of Innovation (X2) on job satisfaction (Y). Based on the path analysis method estimation table, the CR Value is $2.089 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.037, which means it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_0 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Jihanti Dama, Imelda WJ Ogi (2018) with results that prove that innovation partially has a significant effect on satisfied and employees.

Effect of Competence on Employee Satisfaction

The third hypothesis test states that there is an influence of competence (X3) on employee satisfaction (Y). Based on the estimation table for the path analysis method, the CR Value is $2.027 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.043, meaning that it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_0 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Widhijatmiko Setyo Nugroho, Endah

Winarti HS, & M. Taufiq (2019) with results proving that competence affects satisfaction employee. Competence has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction employee.

The effect of Information Technology on Employee Performance

The fourth hypothesis test states that there is an influence of Information Technology (X1) on employee performance (Z). Based on the estimation table of the path analysis method, the CR Value is $2.033 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.042 which means it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_a is accepted. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Agil Rakhmansyah, M. Al Musadieq, and Heru Susilo (2014) with results that prove that wireless information technology and wireline information technology simultaneously have a significant effect on performance. Information Technology positive and significant effect on the employee performance.

Influence Competence on Employee Performance

The fifth hypothesis test states that there is a positive influence between job satisfaction variables on employee performance. This is shown from the value of the estimation table for the path analysis method, the CR Value is $2.031 > 1.96$, while the P value (P-value) is 0.042, meaning it is below 0.05 (5%) then H_a is accepted. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by I Putu Ari Saputra, I Wayan Bagia, I Wayan Suwendra (2016) with results that prove that there is a positive and significant influence of competence on employee work discipline.

Scratch Information Technology on Employee Performance with Satisfaction Work as an Intervening Variable

The sixth hypothesis test states that there is no positive effect between the variables information Technology on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. This is shown from the value of the indirect effect obtained by multiplying the coefficient of the path analysis directly variable information Technology on employee performance with the path analysis coefficient of the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance, namely $-0.039 \times 0.554 = -0.022$, which means H_0 is rejected.

Effect Competence on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable

The seventh hypothesis test states that there is a positive influence between the variables competence on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. This is shown from the value of the indirect effect obtained by multiplying the coefficient of the path analysis directly variable competence on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

IV. CONCLUSION

Information technology has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction. This shows that the information technology used by employees is in accordance with the work they do so that employees feel satisfied. Innovation has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction. This shows that employees must have innovation in increasing job satisfaction, this can affect employee activities at work. Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction. This shows that employees must have the competence to increase job satisfaction. Information technology has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This shows that the existing information technology in the company can support employee performance. Competence has a positive effect on employee performance. This shows that employees who have competence will improve the performance of these employees. Employee satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. This shows that

employee satisfaction can affect performance improvement for employees.

V. Recommendation

Companies need to use technology this is good, because this can make employees feel satisfied and excited to always give their best performance for the company in accordance with the efforts they have done. Companies must create good innovations so that they can give employees a sense of satisfaction and enthusiasm to improve their performance. The innovations created by the company can create a harmonious relationship between fellow employees and superiors and can introduce organizational culture in the company's external environment.

The company needs to improve the competence of its employees by facilitating activities that can improve employee competence, usually by carrying out development, namely through education and training that is carried out regularly, both internally and externally. This can spur job satisfaction and improve employee performance. The company is expected to be able to further increase employee job satisfaction so that in their work employees can be more motivated to work hard. Job satisfaction can be increased by placing employees in accordance with their fields of ability and leadership that always motivates and supervises every work done by employees.

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